

Flexurba 0.2.0: delineating urban boundaries with different types of data and thresholding approaches

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Summary

The article introduces a new version of the *Flexurba* package. This version allows users to create urban boundaries using multiple datasets – including population, built-up area, and night-time light grids – and supports different thresholding methods. Here, we highlight the most significant changes and demonstrate a new functionality. We show how to delineate urban areas in Egypt and Sudan by applying (a) a predefined absolute threshold and (b) a data-driven relative threshold, using both population, built-up area and light intensity data. *Flexurba* 0.2.0 can be explored on [this website](#).

KEYWORDS: R package, urban delineation, thresholds

1. Introduction

Flexurba is an open-source R package designed to flexibly reconstruct the *Degree of Urbanisation* (DEGURBA; Dijkstra et al., 2021) classification of cities, towns, and rural areas (Van Migerode et al., 2024). At GISRUK 2024, *Flexurba* was granted the GoFundGeo Award, co-funded by GISRUK and OSGeo:UK. This award was offered to a tool or technique with the potential for wide uptake in the open-source geospatial community. Thanks to the generous support of this award and ongoing support from Research Foundation Flanders (FWO), we have continued to develop the package and can now announce *Flexurba* 0.2.0. The core idea remains to enable the construction of flexible urban delineations that can be tailored to specific applications or research questions. While the package was initially designed to reconstruct the DEGURBA classification, *Flexurba* now expands its focus to a broader range of delineation approaches.

Since its release, we have received valuable feedback from the user community. Most of the questions we received focused on integrating the output into broader R workflows – e.g. “*How can I overlay the city classification with another shapefile?*” or “*How do I compute aggregate statistics for the different classes?*” Suggestions for new functionalities revolved around operations already possible within the existing R ecosystem and extended beyond DEGURBA – e.g. “*Can thresholds be applied to another type of grid?*”. This feedback underscored that potential users of *Flexurba* are primarily seeking convenience functions that simplify and streamline analyses with, and based on, urban delineations for relatively new R users.

To meet these requests, we added several convenience functions to the package. As such, *Flexurba* 0.2.0 enables the creation of urban boundaries using multiple data sets – including population, built-up area, and night-time light grids – and supports different thresholding approaches, including predefined

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and data-driven thresholds. The most significant modifications are outlined below.

- **Provision of pre-processed datasets:**
We developed the accompanying *FlexurbaData* package with pre-processed population, built-up area, and night-time light grids to facilitate the exploration of delineations based on different data products.
- **Thresholding functions:**
Flexurba 0.2.0 offers a function to construct urban boundaries with different thresholding approaches. The value of the threshold can be (a) predefined by the user or (b) derived from the underlying data. Additionally, it can be (a) enforced consistently across the study area (i.e. an absolute approach) or (b) tailored within a specific country (i.e. a relative approach).
- **Logical combination of thresholds and data sets:**
A new vignette explains how to delineate urban areas by combining thresholds on different data products with logical operators. For instance, urban areas can be defined as: (*light intensity above threshold OR built-up above threshold*) AND *population above threshold*.
- **Renaming and updating the DEGURBA functions:**
The DEGURBA-specific functions have been renamed with the prefix ‘DoU_’ to avoid confusion with the broader urban delineation functionalities. In addition, some functions are updated to reflect to modifications made to the DEGURBA methodology in July 2024.

As an illustration of the potential of *Flexurba 0.2.0*, we focus on one specific new functionality: the thresholding function. We will discuss the rationale behind different thresholding approaches and demonstrate their usage, using the examples of Egypt and Sudan.

2. Predefined absolute thresholds vs. data-driven relative thresholds

Constructing boundaries from gridded data typically requires setting rules to differentiate urban from rural areas. Most approaches rely on thresholds to guide this process. Thresholding approaches generally vary across two aspects. First, how/where the threshold is enforced: (a) consistently across the study area (= absolute approach), or (b) tailored in a specific country/region (= relative approach). Second, how the threshold value is determined: (a) predefined by the user or (b) derived from the underlying data.

Absolute thresholds are applied consistently across the study. These thresholds are easy to interpret and enhance regional comparability (Dijkstra et al., 2021). Nevertheless, given the diverse urbanisation patterns worldwide, it is debatable whether a single, fixed threshold is equally fit in different regions (Potts, 2018). In contrast, relative thresholds are tailored to each country's specific urbanisation pattern or context, and their value thus varies across space. Relative, country-tailored thresholds are useful when informing local policy frameworks or describing urbanisation patterns in the context of a country's historical development (Combes et al., 2023). However, for consistent international comparisons, absolute thresholds are likely more adequate (Dijkstra et al., 2021).

Besides how/where a threshold is enforced, there is also considerable debate on how its value should be determined: (a) predefined by the user or (b) data-driven. Data-driven approaches partly reduce the arbitrary nature of predefined thresholds. However, it is debatable whether data-driven values are, in fact, more suitable than expert knowledge. In addition, data-driven approaches still require the user to make other key operational choices, including the method to infer threshold values from the data and the spatial scale at which separate thresholds should be applied, e.g. per continent, country or state (Duranton, 2021). In that sense, issues related to arbitrariness are not eliminated but moved from the threshold value to the thresholding method.

With *Flexurba 0.2.0*, we do not advocate for either approach but want to offer fellow researchers the opportunity to explore and evaluate different approaches to make an informed decision. To this end, the package includes a dedicated function, `apply_threshold`, that implements multiple thresholding approaches.

Code Example 1 demonstrates how to use the function to construct urban boundaries for Egypt and Sudan using three different data products. For the data-driven relative approach, the threshold is calculated for each country separately as the 99th percentile value of the data distribution (cf. `fun = 'p99'`). The variables `populationdata`, `builtdata`, and `lightdata` represent the gridded population, built-up area, and night-time light data for this region[§] and the object `countries` contains a shapefile of the countries' borders.

```
library(flexurba)

# (A) absolute threshold of 2000 inhab./km²
pop_abs <- apply_threshold(grid = populationdata, type='predefined',
                          threshold_value = 2000)

# (B) absolute threshold of 10% built-up fraction
bui_abs <- apply_threshold(grid = builtdata, type='predefined',
                          threshold_value = 0.10)

# (C) absolute threshold of 15 nW/cm²/sr
ntl_abs <- apply_threshold(grid = lightdata, type='predefined',
                          threshold_value = 15)

# (D) relative threshold of 99th percentile value per country
pop_rel <- apply_threshold(grid = populationdata, type='data-driven',
                          fun = 'p99', regions = countries)

# (E) relative threshold of 99th percentile value per country
bui_rel <- apply_threshold(grid = builtdata, type='data-driven',
                          fun = 'p99', regions = countries)

# (F) relative threshold of 99th percentile value per country
ntl_rel <- apply_threshold(grid = lightdata, type='data-driven',
                          fun = 'p99', regions = countries)
```

Code Example 1 Constructing urban boundaries by enforcing predefined absolute thresholds and data-driven relative thresholds on gridded population, built-up area and night-time light intensity data.

The delineations generated by the code example are shown in Figure 1. When data-driven relative thresholds are enforced, Sudan appears more urbanised across all data products than when predefined absolute thresholds are enforced. The urban developments along the Nile River, particularly downstream from Khartoum, remain obscured with the predefined absolute approach. In contrast, the agglomeration around the Nile Delta in Egypt is always identified. This difference between Sudan and Egypt is driven by (1) the specific values of our predefined thresholds and (2) the variations in the population, built-up area, and light intensity distributions between the two countries. The 99th percentile of the population density is 2098 inhabitants/km² in Egypt but only 282 inhabitants/km² in Sudan. Similarly, the proportion of built-up area at the 99th percentile is 9.4% and 1.4% in Egypt and Sudan, and for night intensity, these values are 14 and 0.3 nW/cm²/sr, respectively. The data-driven thresholds in Sudan are thus significantly lower than our chosen predefined values, leading to the identification of more urban areas.

[§] The GHS-POP layer (Schiavina et al., 2023), GHS-BUILT-S layer (Pesaresi & Politis, 2023), and VIIRS data (Elvidge et al., 2021) of 2020 are employed, respectively.

Figure 1 Urban areas constructed in Code Example 1 with (A) 2000 inhab./km², (B) 10% built-up area, (C) 15 nW/cm²/sr, (D) 99th percentile value of population per country, (E) 99th percentile value of built-up area per country, and (F) 99th percentile value of light intensity per country.

3. Conclusion

By developing and openly sharing *Flexurba 0.2.0*, we offer fellow researchers and practitioners the opportunity to construct and explore custom urban delineations in an easy and accessible manner. In this article, we briefly demonstrated the new function that implements different thresholding approaches. However, the updated package includes other convenience functions for constructing urban boundaries. We would like to encourage researchers to explore (combinations of) different types of data and thresholding methods and critically think about what delineation best works in the context of their application.

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Biographies

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